

THE EFFECT OF DISCOVERY LEARNING MODEL AND STUDENT CREATIVITY ON ENGLISH LEARNING RESULT

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ABSTRACT

This study is aimed to know : 1) The difference of English learning outcomes of the students who learned with the discovery learning model, 2) The effect of interaction between discovery learning model and creativity on English learning outcomes , (3) the difference learning English outcomes on students who learned with discovery learning model with students who learned with expository teaching model on students who have high learning creativity, (4) the difference of English learning outcomes on students who learned with the discovery learning model with students who learned with expository teaching model on students with low learning Creativity.

The populations in this study were all students of second semester of Jakarta Islamic University totaling 432 students. The research sample set was taken 78 students which was a third semester class of Islamic Educational Faculty of Jakarta Islamic University

This study used the 2x2 factorial design , sample through random sampling technique from second semester students , for class experiment (39 students) and a control class (39 students), for the level of creativity is taken by a questionnaire.

To prove the hypotheses testing results : 1) students' English learning outcomes who learned with discovery learning model higher than students who learned with expository teaching model ,with signifikansi $0.019 < 0.05$), 2) There is an interaction effect between learning model with the creativity of students' English learning outcomes, with the $F_b = 9,439 > F_t = 4,325$. 3). students' English learning outcomes who learned with discovery learning model is higher than those who learned with expository teaching model on students who have high creativity , the (degree sign $0.047 < 0.05$) . 4) The results of students' English learning who learned with discovery learning model is higher than who learned with expository teaching model on students who have low creativity.

Conclusion that the discovery learning model is quite effective in improving English learning outcomes.

Key Words: Discovery Learning model, creativity, learning outcomes, Expository.

A. Introduction

A teacher should be able to design instructional based on models, strategies, methods and approaches that involve students directly interact with learning resources, so that knowledge acquired is more memorable and not easily forgotten, or that called the student-centered learning (student oriented). But the problems often experienced that is teacher teaching still maintain teacher oriented, teachers are still dominant as transformation the subject matter from the teacher to the students.

Results of the final exams of the semester school year 2015/2016 in getting the data that the English learning results is still low.

Table 1. Score of English Subject school Year 2012-2017

No	School Year	The average score	Stand ard score	Note
		English		
1.	2012/2013	5.22	6,50	
2.	2014/2015	5.46	6,50	
3.	2016/2017	4.69	6,50	

So far students, having already become a habit as recipients of knowledge, they already feel comfortable with the condition received and not trained to look for, every time when the teacher gives the lessons students to become less active. As a result teacher plays more a role in the learning process. In this case the learning less developed the ability of students. Students become less active, less creative and boring. Due to not having a meaningful learning experience, its impact upon the student's attitude towards the lessons, less fun, less creative.

Based on the author examined, the students often just memorize concepts without knowing how it was obtained. So that students understand and easy to forget about what has been learned and eventually became one of the causes of low student learning outcomes.

B. Literature Review

1. Models of Discovery Learning Learning

Discovery Learning is a learning theory is defined as a process of learning that occurs when lessons are not presented with lessons in the form of the finale, but it is expected students to organize their own, Hamdani (2012). In line with that Sadirman (2001) suggested a Model of Discovery is the mental process when students are assimilated to a concept or a principle, in the form of mental process observe, describe, classify, make conclusions and so on.

Discovery has the same meaning with the Inquiry which means finding or discovery, but there is a difference of opinion by experts regarding the use of the term: the term of the first discovery and inquiry can be defined with the same purpose and use alternating each other or both at once, second, the discovery though generally refers to the same sense with the inquiry but in fact have a difference.

But according to the implementing Committee (2011) on discovery learning and inquiry about the same only it on procedure and outcomes, in inquiry learning outcomes are not known by students or teachers in the teachers guide student discovery found the expected outcomes.

Discovery Learning is a fundamental form of inquiry-oriented learning, discovery Learning learning focus is not on finding applications of knowledge but on building up knowledge from experience.

The model of the Discovery of some experts argue as follows:

- 1). According to Wenning by Denok, the primary goal at this level in pedagogy is Student develop concepts on the

basis of first hand experiences, with focus on active engagement to construct knowledge, according to Sund in Hamdani said that the use of the discovery in a certain boundaries is good for low grade while the inquiry is good for the students classes high, Rusman (2010).

Model study of inquiry and discovery (search and find) is a learning model that was developed based on the view of Constructivism. Both are in principle the same, namely the system of learning that helps students both individually and group learning to find themselves in accordance with their respective experiences. This model emphasizes the importance of understanding the structure or ideas important to a scientific discipline, through involvement of students actively in the learning process.

According to Brunner by Sofyan, Discovery Learning , which stressed the importance of helping students understand the structure of ideas or subject matter will be the involvement of students and the belief that learning actually occurs through invention, Sofyan (2010)

There are two levels of inquiry based on the variations of form and intensity of involvement of students that is free inquiry and inquiry social interactions (guided inquiry) according to Orlich in Sofyan stated that Discovery learning he termed inquiry (guided social interactions inquiry) because students are carefully guided to find answers to the problems that they faced in social interactions or inquiry discovery learning and learning activities must be well managed by teachers and learning outputs can be predicted early .

Discovery learning is one of the learning models used in modern constructivist approach. On learning of the

discovery, students are encouraged to learn by themselves primarily through active involvement with the concepts and principles. Teachers encourage students to have experience and experiment with allowing them to find principles or concepts for themselves.

Learning by Discovery learning is a learning model that is set up in such a way so that children acquire knowledge of yet he knew it was not through notifications, partially or completely found oneself.

Orlich in Sofyan stated there are some characteristics of inquiry social interactions or discovery learning to note, namely: 1) develop the ability to think through a specific observation until students are able to make inference or generalization. 2) goal is to study the process of observation events or objects and compose the appropriate generalization. 3) Teachers to control certain parts of the study, for example, events, data, materials and serves as the leader of the class. 4). Each student is trying to build a meaningful pattern based on the results of observation in the classroom. 5) Class serves as a learning laboratory. 6) is usually a number of generalizations will be retrieved from the students. 7) Teachers motivate all students to communicate the results of generalizations about it so it can be utilized throughout the students in class, according to Saiful (2010) with six stages in implementing the approach/discovery: inquiry as seen in the following table

Table 2. Steps of Learning *Discovery Learning*

Steps	<i>Model Discovery</i>	Activities Description
Introduction	1. Creating a situation (Stimulation)	Concentration: <input type="checkbox"/> Teachers ask questions, with the aim to enable students Pe
Core Activities	1.Problems identifications 2.Data collections/ Observations 3.Data processing 2. verification	<input type="checkbox"/> gives the opportunity to students to identify and analyse the problems they face. <input type="checkbox"/> data collection through a variety of relevant information, read the literature, observe the objec or doing a test run of its own. <input type="checkbox"/> Data acquired is distributed, as the formation of concepts and generalizations, <input type="checkbox"/> carefully Inspection to check the validity of hypotheses that are assigned, or answered whether or not
Final	3. verification	<input type="checkbox"/> draw conclusions. having regard to the results of the verification.

2. The research Hypothesis

Based on the theoretical description, the research hypothesis is formulated as follows:

1. The results of the English learning of students who learned with discovery models is higher compared with students who learned with expository model.
2. There is the influence of the interaction between the discovery model with the creativity of students toward English learning outcomes.
- 3 The results of the English learning of students who learned with discovery models is higher compared with students who learned with the expository for students who have high creativity.
4. The results of the English learning of students who learned with discovery models is lower compared with students who learned with the expository for students who have low creativity.

B. Methodology

1. Model And Design Research

This research model used a quantitative approach in the form of experimentation. The data analysis used test validity and reliability, continued to its homogeneity and normality test, test f ANAVA countdown with two lines using IBM SPSS software 19.

Design method used in this research with a 2 x 2 Factorial design as follows.

Tabel 3. Research Desiugn

Instruc. Model (A) Kreativitas Siswa,(B)	<i>Discovery Learning Model</i> (A₁)	Ekspositori Model (A₂)
High Creativity (B ₁)	A₁B₁	A₂B₁
Low Creativity (B ₂)	A₁B₂	A₂B₂

2. Population and Sampling Techniques

a. Population

In this study the population is the second semester students of Islamic Educational Faculty, Jakarta Islamic University 2016/2017 academic year totaling 432 students.

b. Sample

In this study, there were two classes of samples from five parallel classes with a total number of students 78. The sampling technique in this study was by Random Sampling technique, experiment class and control class, as seen in the following table:

Table 4. Sampel

Populasi	Sampel	Jumlah	Keterangan
Second semester students	Kelas A	39	Kelas Eksperimen
	Kelas B	39	Kelas Kontrol

3. Data Collection Techniques

For data collection, the authors used two instruments, namely a questionnaire instrument to measure student creativity and test instruments to measure learning outcomes

a. Instrument Calibration

1. Student learning outcomes

(1). Validity

The quality of the instrument is shown by validity and reliability in expressing what will be measured.

To find out the validity of the item, biserial points correlation (r_{pbis}) is used, while reliability used KR-20.

(2). Validity of Questions with Biserial Points

$$r_{pbis} = \frac{M_p - M_t}{SD_t} \sqrt{\frac{P}{q}}$$

(2) Instrument Reliability

Instrument Reliability was calculated using the KR-20 formula as shown in the follows:

$$r = \frac{k}{k-1} \frac{SDt^2 \sum pq}{SDt^2}$$

2. Learning Creativity

(1). Validity test

Test the validity of students' creativity learning instruments used Pearson's Prodak Moment formula.

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n(\sum XY) - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{[n(\sum X^2) - (\sum X)^2][n(\sum Y^2) - (\sum Y)^2]}}$$

(2). Reliability Test

The calibration reliability of the creativity questionnaire was tested using Alpha Cronbach formula as follows:

$$r = \left(\frac{k}{k-1} \right) \left(1 - \frac{\sum si^2}{\sum st^2} \right)$$

Based on the results of the pilot test data using ANANTES, the creativity questionnaire instrument of 36 students obtained r reliability coefficient of 0.87 thus, it can be concluded that the instrument of student creativity has a very high level of reliability.

C. Result

1. Hypothesis Testing

Testing the hypothesis in this study was carried out using two-way ANOVA analysis, followed by the Tukey test.

Based on the results of the two ANOVA calculations using SPSS 19 the following data was obtained.

Table 4.10 ANOVA Test 2 Pathways to Learning Outcomes

Between-Subjects Factors

Model		Value Label	N
Learning	1	Discovery Learning	22
Creativity	2	Expository Learning	22
	1	High	22
	2	Low	22

Table 5 Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Variable: Learning outcomes	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	21466,419 ^a	3	7155,473	108,215	,000
Intercept	159774,39	1	159774,39	2416,341	,000
Model	392,579	1	392,579	5,937	,019
Creativity	20449,722	1	20449,722	309,270	,000
Model *	624,119	1	624,119	9,439	,004
Creativity					
Error	2644,898	40	66,122		
Total	183885,71	44			
Corrected Total	24111,317	43			

19 calculation table, the ANOVA test of the two paths above can be used to answer the first and second hypotheses, such as:

1. Differences in English Learning Outcomes Between Students Who Are Learned Using Discovery Learning Models (A1) With Students Who Are Learned using Expository Learning Models (A2).

The decision making standard is based on the following probability values:

a) If the probability value is > 0.05 then H_0 is accepted. H_1 rejected

B) If the probability value is < 0.05 , H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted

Based on the results of the calculations shown in table 4.12 Anova test results, that $F_{count} = 5.937$ and $F_{table} 4.325$.

with a significant level or probability of 0.019. Because the result is smaller than 0.05 (Significant < 0.05)

Then there are differences in learning outcomes between students who use discovery learning models (A1) with students who are taught with an expository learning model (A2). Can also be seen from the average score (A1) = 69.15 and (A2) = 64.2

2. Effect of Interaction Between the Use of Learning Models (A) and Student Learning Creativity (B) on English Learning Outcomes. A * B)

The decision making standard is based on the following probability values:

a) If the probability value / Sign > 0.05 then H_0 is accepted. H_1 is rejected

b) If the probability value / Sign < 0.05 then H_0 is rejected and

H1 is accepted.

Based on the results of the calculations shown in table 4.12 of the ANOVA test results, that $F_{\text{arithmetic}} = 9.439$ and $F_{\text{table}} = 4.325$. with a significant level or probability of 0.04.

Because the result is smaller than 0.05 (Significant < 0.05)

Then there is interaction between students who use discovery learning (A1) learning models with students who are taught with an expository learning model (A2). It can also be obtained from the average score (A1) = 69.15 and (A2) = 64.21.

For students who teach with an expository learning model (A2). It can also be obtained from the average score (A1) = 69.15 and (A2) = 64.21.

1. Differences in English Outcomes Between Students Learning the Discovery Learning Model (A1) with Expository Learning (A2) for Students Who Have High Creativity (B1)

The decision making standard is based on the following probability values:

- a) If the probability value is > 0.05 then H_0 is accepted. H_1 is rejected
- b) If the probability value is < 0.05 , H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted.

Based on the calculation results shown in table 4.12 the results of the 1-way ANOVA test and continued by the Tukey test using SPSS 19 statistics are shown in the table below

Table 4.11 Anova Test 1 Path Description of Calculation Results of Differences in Science Learning Outcomes Between Students Learning the Discovery Learning Model (A1) with Expository (A2) learning on Students Who Have High Creativity (B1)

Descriptives Hasil Uji Anova 1

Result of Anova	N	Mean	Std. Deviatio	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Min	Max
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test					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
A1B1	11	89,27	6,262	1,888	85,07	93,48	77	97
A1B2	11	45,36	11,952	3,604	37,33	53,39	29	66
A2B1	11	76,82	8,328	2,511	71,22	82,41	66	91
A2B2	11	58,09	14,666	4,422	48,24	67,94	34	69
Total	44	67,39	19,999	3,015	61,31	73,47	29	97

Result of ANOVA Test	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	12533,159	3	4177,720	35,820	,000
Within Groups	4665,273	40	116,632		
Total	17198,432	43			

Table 4.12 Calculation Results of the Tukey Test of the Difference in English Learning Outcomes Between Students Learning the Discovery Learning Model (A1) with Expository Learning (A2) on Students Who Have High Creativity (B1

Multiple Comparisons

Result Tukey HSD

(I) Model	(J) Model	N	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
A1B1	A1B2		43,91	4,605	,000	31,57	56,25
	A2B1	11	12,45	4,605	,047	,11	24,80
	A2B2		31,18	4,605	,000	18,84	43,53
A1B2	A1B1		-43,91	4,605	,000	-56,25	-31,57
	A2B1	11	-31,45	4,605	,000	-43,80	-19,11
	A2B2		-12,73	4,605	,041	-25,07	-,38
A2B1	A1B1		-12,45	4,605	,047	-24,80	-,11

	A1B2	11	31,45	4,605	,000	19,11	43,80
	A2B2		18,73	4,605	,001	6,38	31,07
A2B2	A1B1		-31,18	4,605	,000	-43,53	-18,84
	A1B2	11	12,73	4,605	,041	,38	25,07
	A2B1		-18,73	4,605	,001	-31,07	-6,38

Based on the two results, the calculation of 1-way Anava and Tukey test because the results are smaller than 0.05 (Significant <0.05). Then there are differences in the results of learning English between students who are taught with discovery learning (A1) models with expository learning (A2) in students who have high creativity

As the results of the descriptive analysis above can be concluded as follows:

That the group of students of English learning outcomes on students who were taught using discovery learning models on those with high creativity (A1B1) obtained an average value of 89.27 and a standard Deviation of 4.58, and a maximum score of 97, a minimum score of 77 and a student group Learning English for students who are taught using expository models in those with high creativity (A2B1) obtained an average value of 76.82 Standard Deviation 8,328. maximum 91 minimum value 66 .

Based on the results of testing the hypothesis obtained significance test results 0.47 shows that sig <0.05 so that it can be concluded that the learning outcomes of English in students who learned using discovery learning models in those who have higher creativity higher than English learning outcomes for students who are taught to use expository models on those who have high creativity (A1B1> A2B1).

1. Differences in the results of learning English between students who are taught with discovery learning (A1) models with Expository learning (A2) on students who have low creativity (B2)

To answer the fourth hypothesis, it still refers to table 4.12 of 1-way Anava test and Tukey test.

The A1B2 group of students obtained an average value of 45.36 standard deviations 14.66 max value = 66, the value of min = 29 and the group of students A2B2 obtained an average value of 58.09 standard deviation 2.30. Based on the results of testing the hypothesis obtained significance test results of 0.41 showed that sig < 0.05 so it can be concluded that the results of learning English in students who learned using discovery learning models in those who have lower creativity compared to the results of learning English in students who learned using the model expository in those with low creativity (A1B1 $<$ A2B2).

C. Discussion

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it turns out that the four proposed alternative hypotheses are significantly acceptable. The description of each acceptance of the three hypotheses in question can be explained as follows:

1. The first hypothesis, examines the differences in learning outcomes of natural science between students who are taught using the Discovery Learning learning model with students who are taught with the Expository learning model. this analysis proved that $F_h = 5,397$ and $F_t = 4,325$ ($f_{count} > f_{table}$) that $F_{count} = 5,397$ and $F_{table} = 4,325$. with a significant level

or probability of 0.019. Because the result is smaller than 0.05 (Significant <0.05) Then (H_0) = rejected and H_1 is accepted, (H_0) or statistical hypothesis which states that there is no difference in Natural Science learning outcomes that get the treatment of discovery learning models with students who are taught with an expository learning model. And H_1 is accepted. this means that there are differences in learning outcomes between students who use discovery learning learning models with students who are taught with an expository learning model. The testing of this hypothesis also proves that discovery learning model provides opportunities for students to be actively involved in finding concepts directly in learning, this allows students to improve learning outcomes.

1. Testing the second hypothesis examines the interaction between the use of discovery learning models and the learning creativity of the results of English learning. if that $F_{5,397} > F_{4,325}$. with a significant level or probability of 0.019. smaller than 0.05
(Significant <0.05) H_1 is accepted. H_0 rejected H_1 accepted. This means that there is an interaction between students who use discovery learning models, with students who are taught with an expository learning model
Therefore, it was concluded that the achievement of learning outcomes in English was influenced by the interaction of discovery learning models and learning creativity.
2. Testing the third hypothesis, that there are differences in the results of learning English between students who use discovery

learning model is higher than the model of expository learning in students who have high learning creativity. This is based on the results of testing hypotheses through the Tukey test obtained significance test results 0.47 shows that sig <0.05 so that it can be concluded that the learning outcomes of English in students who learned using discovery learning models in those who have higher creativity compared to the results of learning English for students who are taught using expository models on those who have high creativity, this is because students with high creativity are directly involved in processing their knowledge so as to enable them to improve their learning outcomes.

4. Testing the fourth hypothesis, that there are differences in the results of students' English learning between those who use discovery learning model is lower than the model of expository learning in students who have low learning creativity. This is based on the results of testing hypotheses through the Tukey test obtained significance test results 0.41 shows that sig <0.05 so it can be concluded that the results of learning English in students who learned using discovery learning models in those with low creativity is lower than the results of the expository model in students who have low creativity. This is because students who have low creativity are not directly involved fully in processing their own knowledge, for students who have low creativity or do not want to increase their creativity are not suitable to use discovery learning models, because teachers still have to be dominant. So that the learning outcomes of students who have low creativity are less optimal learning outcomes.

D. Conclusion

Based on data obtained in the field, the results of testing hypotheses and discussion of research results, the authors can draw some conclusions as follows; ,

1) That there are differences in the results of learning English between students who are taught using the Discovery Learning model with students who are taught with the Expository learning model, with a significance of $0.019 < 0.05$ or $F_h = 5.397 > F_t. 4.325$. This means that the results of learning English, with the model of Discovery Learning is higher than the results of learning English using an expository learning model. This shows that the use of Discovery learning models can be used to improve English learning outcomes.

2) There is an influence of the interaction between the learning model and students' creativity on the learning outcomes of English, with a significant price of $F_h = 9.439 > F_t = 4.08.3$). meaning that the learning outcomes of English are influenced by the use of student learning models and creativity

3) There are differences in the results of learning English for students who are taught using the Discovery Learning model with students who are taught using the Expository learning model for students who have Higher Learning Creativity, with (sign level $0.047 < 0.05$). that English learning outcomes with discovery learning models are higher or better than students who are taught expository models to students who have high creativity.

use the Discovery Learning learning model with students who are taught using the Expository learning model for students who have Higher Learning Creativity, with (sign level $0.047 < 0.05$). that English learning outcomes with discovery learning models are higher or better than students who are taught expository models to students who have high creativity.

4) The results of learning English in students who use the Discovery Learning model is lower than students who use the Expository learning model for students who have Low Learning Creativity.

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